

PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF FAMILIES ON THE EDGE OF DIVORCE

Urdabayeva Gulnora Mambetaliyevna

Gulistan State University

Teacher of the Department of Psychology

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8046827>

Annotation. This article discusses the socio-psychological characteristics of the reasons for coming to the brink of divorce. The studies conducted in the world and in Uzbekistan are analyzed. The article gives psychological advice on preventing of divorces.

Keywords: family, psychological, divorce, marriage, recommendation

The family is the main link of the society, and a stable family is important for the improvement of the population's well-being, especially for the economic development. Family disputes, on the contrary, have a negative impact on the quality of life of family members, raising children, and cause sharp social conflicts and dangers. Taking into account that divorce threatens the economic and social stability of the country, many scientists have begun to research the factors that increase the risk of divorce.

Observing the historical trends in the process of family transformation, we witness the increasing number of family divorces in the initial stages of the liberalization and industrialization of society. At the same time, some scientists put forward the idea that "when the development reaches a certain point, the stability of the marriage will be restored."

It is known that the causes of family separation are influenced by the geographic location, culture, customs, religion, morals and the level of education and poverty of the population of each country, as well as various economic, social, psychological, internal and external stress factors.

Over the past half century, interest in researching the impact of various socio-economic factors on the transformation of the family structure and family stability has been growing. Some studies have examined the effects of macroeconomic indicators such as inflation and unemployment on divorce, while others have assessed the effects of women's empowerment, education, and other social factors.

G. Becker was the first to study the causes of marriage and family separation from an economic point of view in 1973. G. Becker emphasized that the difference in the income of married and single people depends on non-economic aspects such as the level of education and social status in society. Becker and his supporters later argued that unexpected life events increase the risk of divorce by affecting earnings. Hoffman and Duncan, who extensively studied the effects of women's income and employment on divorce, found that families with higher male incomes were less likely to divorce, and in a study by Oppenheimer, the risk of divorce increased as women became more independent. Another notable study examined the effect of socioeconomic factors on divorce in Iran, using the Gini index (GINI) to find that the quality of the income distribution worsened, resulting in an increase in divorce. Also, it has been scientifically proven that urbanization and the increase in household expenses lead to an

increase in the number of divorces, and an increase in literacy and per capita income leads to a decrease in family divorces.

In 1989, scientists such as K. Trent and S. Southx conducted an in-depth analysis of the influence of individual factors on divorce, as a result of which the reasons for the differences in the divorce rate around the world were studied. In the course of this research, using a sample consisting of 66 countries, the level of importance of the gender ratio in the decision to divorce between women, the participation of women in the labor market, the age of marriage, religious views was determined.

Age, period and cohort. In the 1980s, scientists focused on aspects of family separations related to time (age periods). In almost all studies, special attention is paid to the fact that the age at the time of starting a family has a strong influence on family decisions, and the formation of common views on marriage among people of different age groups. Also, scientists have emphasized the importance of analyzing people's age at the time of divorce.

Children. Conceiving a child is one of the main goals of starting a family. Initially, scientists suggested that the presence of children in the family, especially if they are young, reduces the likelihood of divorce. It was later found that second and subsequent children increased the risk of divorce in Denmark while strengthening the family in Italy and Spain. Therefore, the influence of children on family stability can change depending on the moral and cultural values formed in the society.

Employment and income. Early research on this topic found that the risk of divorce is minimal when one spouse is gainfully employed and the other earns a living. The increased risk of divorce as a result of increased financial resources of women is referred to as the "freedom effect". The strengthening of the family due to the financial resources of the wife is called "income effect". Many scientists believed that the "freedom effect" is higher than the "income effect" and leads to a decrease in its positive aspects. However, modern trends show that in many countries, both spouses being employed increases family income and improves marital stability. In addition, there is evidence that a higher salary of a man reduces the probability of divorce, and a higher salary of a woman increases this risk. In fact, a woman's level of employment and income does not reduce the quality of the marriage, but only reduces the barriers to exit from an inappropriate, problematic marriage. In order to empirically verify this idea, scientists have included the concepts of marriage quality or measures of happiness in their research. Changes such as a sudden increase or decrease in income, a period of crisis, also increase the risk of divorce. Differing religious views of spouses also negatively affects family stability.

Migration. Migration is another process that seriously affects the stability of marriage. The family is subjected to additional tests in unfamiliar conditions and may become less resistant to foreign influences. It was found that sometimes the head of the family, sometimes the spouse, moves to a new job in order to earn income, putting the marriage in danger. At this point, let's cite an example from history: Umar ibn Khattab (r.a.) used to go around the city at night without informing anyone, bringing news about the condition of people. One day, they heard a woman reciting verses about hijran in a courtyard. When they inquired, the woman's husband had gone to the military. Hazrat Umar sent someone and asked his daughter Hafsa: "How long can a woman endure without a husband?" He answered: "Four months." After that, Hazrat Umar ordered not to keep anyone in the army for more than four

months. At present, the fact that some people leave their families in foreign countries in order to earn money is causing the destruction of families.

Biological and health-related factors. Much of the research on health and divorce has focused on the effects of divorce on the health of couples and children. At the same time, there are scientific works on the fact that health itself is the cause of divorce. For example, a number of scientists have determined that the risk of divorce increases due to alcoholism and illegal psychotropic drugs, and the birth of a mentally ill or disabled child in the family. For example, in Russia, alcoholism is causing an increase in the divorce rate, a decrease in the birth rate, and an increase in the death rate.

University of Chicago Psychologist John Caccioppo: "Being Lonely" Says John Caccioppo, a psychologist at the University of Chicago: "Admitting to yourself that you are lonely is like writing a big 'Yo' in the middle of your forehead." , - while saying, he draws attention to the fact that the days spent by people with this feeling are hard. According to the expert, it doesn't matter how many people gather around a person. In order not to feel alone, a person needs someone to go to. Taking this into account, in the European countries of England and Denmark, various preventive measures are being carried out for elderly lonely people. An article published in the American Journal of Psychiatry found that married people are less likely to drink than single people. However, studies have shown that being married to a drunkard can cause an alcoholic to drink more or their spouse to become an alcoholic.

"We tried to study how much it affects a person who is married to an alcoholic," says psychiatrist Kenneth Kendler, a professor at the University of Virginia School of Medicine.

Analysis shows that getting married reduces alcoholism by 59% in men and 73% in women. It is especially useful for people who have a history of alcoholism at the time of starting a family. For example, if a husband or wife had a tendency to drink before the wedding, in the future, this stupid habit will make the drunkard's wife a drunkard.

So, starting a family with an alcoholic is worse than living alone. Kenneth Kendler says that scientists are now studying whether alcoholism leads to divorce. According to them, divorce causes an increase in alcoholism.

If a couple's relationship has reached a critical point, only they can solve it. The husband and wife's intention to preserve the family is not enough, they need to work together. It is important to be ready for long and productive life tests with patience and unity to restore relations. If love is preserved in family relationships, it can save the family.

First of all, husband and wife need to understand why they want to divorce. For this, he should think deeply about a worthy cause. Even if couples are compatible, there will always be problems in their relationship. Regardless of who initiated the divorce, if one of the husband or wife wants a divorce, the other cannot do anything alone. To restore the relationship, you just need a lot of effort and desire. The party who wants to save his marriage can have a positive effect on the situation. Psychologists advise this as follows:

- constructive attitude should be initiated;
- it is important to find out why your spouse wants a divorce;
- you need to talk about your willingness to change in order to improve the relationship.

Family is very important to women, so they are often willing to compromise to avoid divorce. Women have the opportunity to influence the decisions of their spouses, for this they must perform the following tasks:

- pay attention to external attractiveness.
- trying to rekindle the fire of extinguished feelings.
- it is not necessary to force, but to give the husband the opportunity to independently analyze and make a decision.
- arouse the interests of the spouse, encourage him to restore the relationship.
- forget complaints and criticisms.
- A woman should start paying more attention to her husband in order to feel her value and importance.

A woman can create the strongest emotional atmosphere in a couple's relationship. Therefore, his efforts will not be without results. If the husband and wife have made the final decision, it is difficult to convince them to rekindle the relationship. In this case, families are separated.

If the woman wants a divorce, but the man wants to save the family, the man can influence his wife's decision. Solving problems in a marriage is the responsibility of two people. What can be done to prevent a man from getting divorced?

- find out what aspects of your spouse you don't like.
- pay more attention to his wife.
- make your spouse feel loved and appreciated.
- give his woman what she lacks.

To save a family on the verge of divorce, it is necessary to take the first step as an example. If a woman notices positive changes in her husband, she can think about her decision.

Psychological studies show that crises in family relationships are more common in the following cases.

The monotony of everyday life. At the beginning of the relationship, everything seems unusual, passionate and full of intense feelings. They seem to be getting to know each other for the first time. No one can harm them because they still enjoy each other's company. Then worries and problems begin to appear. This is mainly due to the same way of life and work. Prolonged homogeneity is the primary cause of crisis. For some, this situation is happy, and for others it is unpleasant. If the life of the couple in the family does not consist of various and unexpected small events, they will get bored of each other. Then he starts looking for interesting things in the circle of friends, outside the house and in other environments. Misunderstandings and betrayals will appear. Women mostly suffer from these incidents, because men act a little more freely. A woman's responsibility towards her children does not allow this.

Financial difficulties. Not every family will be ready to overcome financial problems together. If a woman is not used to spending money correctly and purposefully in the family, if she does not know how to save, she will be reprimanded by her husband for her wasted money. Excess expenses harm the family economy. In such cases, the couple is not satisfied with each other, a family crisis begins. Today, it has become common for young families to get a mortgage loan. It takes a large part of the family income and makes you pay for a long time. A woman always wants to look beautiful, buy new things, jewelry. Money is lacking due to credit. Slanders begin, disputes and quarrels arise. A woman demands that her husband earn more money.

Cooling of emotions. Sexual relations play a crucial role in the development of family relationships. Sex becomes more and more a marital duty. A woman is often busy with housework and other issues and cannot pay attention to her husband's needs. Sometimes women ignore themselves. The husband does not like this situation and starts looking for "another woman". Another one of the crises in family relations starts from this.

The emergence of the above crises and if you are ready to cope with these situations, then you can save your family. For this, you need to realize that you and your spouse have the same goals. For him:

Talk to your spouse. If your partner has made a mistake, you should not immediately speak out loud. Don't analyze his mistake alone. Maybe he has enough problems and he is living with the thought of divorce. Talk directly about your wishes and problems, look for a solution together. It is important to agree on some issues in family life in advance. Please note!!! If you make a habit of doing something without consulting your spouse, he will do the same. Later, he gives up on the idea of living together and being of the same opinion. This has a negative impact on marital relations.

Refrain from arguing and scolding. Both spouses are to blame for disputes and quarrels that cause family crises. Everyone knows that he is innocent. They should be equally responsible in a couple's relationship. Don't always think "I'm right" in everything. Disputes, quarrels and disagreements happen between every couple. Conflict or violence should not be allowed to solve the problem. Because it does not solve family problems, but aggravates them and causes a break in relations. Learn to deal with it peacefully.

Be able to share responsibilities. Divide responsibilities from the first day of your marriage. If you want to help your spouse, do everything together, not for each other. If a mistake is made, ask them not to repeat it. Don't create an unreasonable law that says, "I earn money, you take care of children's education and their lessons." The fate of the child is a joint responsibility, therefore, both father and mother are equally responsible for their education.

Do not discuss your family problems with relatives and friends. A couple is one soul. Your family is yours, not someone else's. Don't publicize your family problems as a community problem. In the first years of marriage, wives like to complain to their parents about the mistakes of their husbands, as if their daughter seems to be suffering in front of them, and interference in their family begins. This makes the situation worse. However, with whom and how you choose to live your life. Therefore, share your family claims with each other, not with others.

Show interest in your spouse's activities. Sometimes when you are busy with daily problems, you forget to ask about your spouse's work activities, jobs, etc. This is also a component of family relations. Today there are no family activities. A couple should respect each other's interests. If the family has common interests, it will have a very positive effect on the strength of the family. Make it a habit to ask about his achievements and the opinion of his colleagues. It will be impressive. The family will be happy.

Change the family environment. If misunderstandings and disagreements begin to arise in your relationship, if you feel that you are in a crisis, immediately change the atmosphere to a positive one. Take a vacation from work and spend it with your spouse. You can do these things even during short breaks. That's when you get to relax and enjoy each other's company. Problems and worries recede. You will realize that the events that caused the problem are not

the main thing. There you can remember happy times with your spouse. A change in environment has a positive effect on relationships and can be restored.

Take time for yourself. You often neglect yourself in family life and solving family problems. Change your appearance and focus on it all the time. Always looking for something new. Then your spouse will never get bored of you.

Sharing warm memories. Remember together the photos of happy days in the past. When you go somewhere, don't forget to take a memorable photo. Make those moments a topic of conversation. Remember together the good and funny situations. You begin to feel that you have a right to be happy. If you don't have pictures of happy days between husband and wife, share memories of relatives or childhood friends.

Gratitude. Often people forget how important it is to feel and express gratitude for having a spouse after living together for a certain period of time. It is necessary to learn to understand and appreciate it. Women are more dissatisfied with their husbands because of family difficulties, especially financial difficulties. At that time, thanking your spouse even in such a situation will make his life easier. Don't overlook the little things.

Marriage and family are values in every person's life. The answer to the question "Should the family be preserved or not?" should always be "yes". In our opinion, it is better to prevent a crisis and divorce than to think about how to get your spouse back after a breakup. If something goes wrong in your family, you are both responsible for it. Someone must be superior in the family. You have the right to start all over again and live happily ever after.

References:

1. Vishnevsky A.G. Izbrannye demograficheskie trudy. - T.1. - Moscow: Nauka, 2005. -120 p.
2. Volkov A.G. Semya - demographics of the object. - Moscow: Mysl, - 106 c.
3. Roussel L. La Famille incertaine. Editions Odibe Jacob, 1989, pp. 1-8
4. Evolution Semi in Europe: East-West. - Moscow: NISP, - S. 188.
5. Becker, G. S. (1973). A Theory of Marriage: Part I. Journal of Political Economy, University of Chicago Press, vol. 81(4), pp. 813-46.
6. Becker, G. S., Landers, E. M., & Michael, R. T. (1977). «An Economic Analysis of Marital Instability» Journal of Political Economy, 85(6), 1141-1187.
7. Hoffman, S. & Duncan, G. (1997). The Effect of Incomes, Wages and Benefits on Marital Disruption. Journal of Human Resources 30, p.194.
8. Oppenheimer, V. (1997). Women's Employment and the Gain to Marriage: The Specialization and Trading Model, Annual Review of Sociology, 23, pp. 431-
9. Musai, M. (2014). Divorce Rate and Economic Factors in Iran. International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences/ March 2014, Vol. 4, No. 3
10. Trent, K. & South, S.J. (1989). Structural Determinants of the Divorce Rate: A Cross-Societal Journal of Marriage and Family, Vol. 51, No., pp. 391-404.
11. Thornton, A. (2005). Reading History Sideways: The Fallacy and Enduring Impact of the Developmental Paradigm on Family Life. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
12. Lyngstad, T., H. & Jalovaara, M. (2010). A review of the antecedents of union dissolution. Demographic research, vol. 23, pp. 257-292.
13. Coppola, L. and Di Cesare, M. (2008). How fertility and union stability interact in shaping new family patterns in Italy and Spain. Demographic Research 18(4), pp. 117-144.

14.Svarer,

and

Verner, M. (2006), Do Children Stabilize Danish Marriages. Journal of Population Economics 21(2), pp. 395-417.

